

Climate Projections in C3S

Gaps in Mitigation Support -- a personal view

Martin Juckes, Nov. 5th, 2019

1. Introduction

C3S has done a remarkable job of pulling together a wide range of data products and establishing a framework for hosting community applications. There is a strong focus on understanding and extracting the value of each category of data. However, I feel that the “value proposition” of the global climate projections is not yet clearly understood. Seeing that C3S has a clear aim to support the IPCC creates some possibilities for improving the situation.

The work of CEDA¹ and collaborators on supplying CMIP5 (Coupled Model Inter-comparison Project Phase 5) data is not likely to deliver high value to the C3S users, partly because the data is becoming obsolete and partly because the value proposition of the data, in the context of adaptation and mitigation, does not fit the CDS model well. The mis-match in timing for CMIP5 was more or less unavoidable. It appears to me that work we might do in the name of C3S on CMIP6 data is also likely to be too late to deliver any benefits to the IPCC, which is unfortunate. I am not keen on doing quality control work on the projections for the IPCC next year (there is a September deadline for inputs to the current assessment cycle²) and then repeating the work a year or two later for C3S. If necessary, it can be done, of course, but it would improve our work in the longer term if we could avoid this duplication.

Table 1. below lists some areas of work which qualify as service activities supporting mitigation and adaptation work with global projections, i.e. CMIP. There are also significant activities supporting research .. but those are out of scope here (examples of excluded service activities are: developing and maintaining climate model codes and infrastructure, configuring models for experiments targeting mitigation and adaptation questions, processing and formatting data to enable the multi-model evaluation). It is not possible to draw a clear line dividing services supporting the IPCC assessment process from those supporting the underlying research. Instead, the approach here is to list service activities which fall substantially within the scope of C3S ambitions.

Table 1: Service activities supporting mitigation and adaptation work with CMIP		
Topic	Service element	Comments
1.Evaluation of climate models and climate model data	Timely completion of analyses designed by IPCC author teams.	Can be delivered in an off-line batch environment. Working through CDS toolkit would involve unacceptable delays. Small number of users, high impact.

1 Centre for Environmental Data Analysis

2 Quality control on the CMIP projections is being done by a variety of projects with a diverse range of aspirations.

2. IPCC Special Reports	Supporting provision of climate projections for special reports such as SR15	When IPCC prepares a high-impact report there is naturally interest in the data from a broad user community.
3. Integrated Assessment Modeling	Providing access to projected emissions.	These models provide the link between policy and emissions scenarios.
4. Maintaining Data Standards	Work on data standards requires a long term commitment.	This work has high impact, but is difficult to fund through research agencies. Well structured standards can also facilitate improvements in the user interfaces by, for instance, enabling smart dataset searches across multiple domains.
5. Monitoring Policy Actions	Making an objective analysis of the link between policy initiative and stated long term goals.	The UK Climate Change Committee performs this function for the UK. Analysing this link requires a combination of climate science and economic policy awareness.

At the moment CEDA and collaborators have three strands of service work: supporting research, supporting the IPCC assessment and supporting C3S services. The boundaries are often blurred, partly because scientific judgment plays a significant role in all three areas, and partly because the whole domain is constantly evolving. It would, however, make our work more effective if we could avoid an artificial boundary between work done supporting the IPCC assessment and work done for C3S.

The QC activities can be funded in the margins of research activities .. but they are not part of the research work. Using piecemeal funding has consequences for the quality of the work done, which creates a need for C3S to repeat the process. It would be more efficient, and deliver greater benefit to the IPCC, if the C3S funded EQC work on climate projections could be done in a timely manner to support the IPCC assessment. Section 2.1 below gives a more detailed description of EQC activities on CMIP climate projections.

2. Technical Overview

2.1 The evaluation of climate models and climate model data

There are several levels of EQC applied to the climate model data going into IPCC reports:

- QC1: Syntax checks on file metadata;
- QC2: Variable level consistency checks;
- QC3: Process level consistency checks.

When CMIP5 data was provided for the IPCC 5th Assessment Report, these checks were not carried out consistently across the full archive. In order to ensure consistent data quality for C3S users, checks in QC1 and QC2 categories have been done for the CMIP5 data under the C3S_34a (Lot 1) contract - these checks are primarily validating the data export procedures at the modeling centres, rather than the models themselves. In the last few days I have had discussions with Anca about how this could become better aligned with the work going on in the EQC contracts in the future, so that when these checks are applied to CMIP6 data the results can, we hope, be presented through the same framework as the EQC results on ECVs etc. However, that the C3S funded work on quality control of CMIP6 is likely to be too late to benefit the IPCC. The value of doing these checks after the IPCC deadline is, unfortunately, going to be less than it might have been. Hence, I would like to broaden the discussion and think how we might reset the process for CMIP7, or for any special report which comes after CMIP6.

Before going into that, I would like to complete the discussion of the three levels of EQC by describing the process level checks (QC3). In an interesting parallel with the CDS toolkit, there is an evaluation environment (ESMVal³) which facilitates the execution of community applications developed to evaluate specific processes. The environment provides access to an extensive collection of observational data used to evaluate the climate models. There are also significant differences: the ESMVal is focused on batch processing; the observations are there to support the evaluation of the climate models; the value proposition comes from delivering the evaluation to the IPCC, not from letting users run it on demand.

Figure 1. shows some example results from work done by Peter Gleckler (PCMDI) on model evaluation. This work goes beyond the QC2 range checks carried out in C3S_34a (Lot 1). Systems to streamline the process have been developed in C3S_34a (Lot 2): these systems are not judged a good fit for the CDS target user audience and might be better suited as part of the EQC suite. The service element of this work involves hosting the software in an environment which has access to the full range of model data and the necessary processing power.

Figure 1: plots showing process-level model evaluation (an example of ESMval output) as calculated for CMIP5 data.

The argument for providing a service to evaluate climate models are:

- (1) this evaluation is required as part of the evidence base for formulation of climate policy;
- (2) this evaluation can be done through research funding, but it is not really a research activity. Consequently, leaving it to the research community is likely to result in piecemeal efforts.
- (3) it is a high impact activity, bringing high returns for modest investment.
- (4) ideally, the evaluation should exploit ECVs and re-analysis data held in the CDS.

The process of setting quality control metrics for CMIP data is complex and diverse. There is no obvious requirement for additional checks to be introduced by C3S. The coordination of the process is poorly funded, but Michel Rixen is trying to develop a WMO process to provide support for some high level support of governance activities. C3S could make a big difference, and a substantial contribution to the IPCC assessment, if the EQC work on climate projections could be aligned with IPCC requirements.

2.2 Data for IPCC Special Report on 1.5 Degree Warming (SR15)

Climate model projections used for the SR15⁴ analysis did not go through the CMIP process, though I believe they used the CMIP5 protocol for the definition of data variables and file formats. The volume of data was considerably smaller than that associated with the CMIP exercises, as the modeling effort was focused on specific science questions rather than providing a comprehensive, process-level, inter-comparison of all the models.

Regarding transparency and consistency, users may expect to find this data in the CDS (given that CDS is claiming to be comprehensive). It may not be a priority to migrate it into

4 Global Warming of 1.5 °C, <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>.

the CDS at this stage, but there would be benefit in providing a service to support the management of data that is needed by the IPCC in the preparation of high profile reports.

2.3 Integrated Assessment Modeling

The work of the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium is not currently reflected in C3S. The associated data volumes are modest, but the data complexity is huge.

This data comes from models which have been used to support the assessment of the economic consequences of different fossil fuel reduction pathways. It is not possible to give users the full picture on how future scenarios relate to policy without information about these models.

IIASA coordinate the creation of the consolidated dataset on behalf of the IAMC and distribute it through their web pages. It may be possible, following the model of the NOAA re-analyses, to give CDS users the benefits of access to this data without replicating quality control and documentation hosted at IIASA.

2.4 Maintaining and Extending Data Standards

Interoperability of data products depends on having standards which need to keep up with the expanding domain of climate science. This work needs to be done well before product publication, because the standardised terminology needs to be built into the workflows around data generation and validation. It is now time to start working on data standards for CMIP7. From the C3S perspective, there will be considerable benefit if the alignment between standards used for CMIP with those used for ECVs and reanalysis products could be improved (e.g. using a common approach for global attributes, for for defining detailed properties of the numerical mesh holding the data).

There is also a need to support users and data providers struggling with differences between different standards. It is possible, for instance, to define mappings between grib variables, ECVs and CF Standard Names, but maintaining an authoritative and comprehensive set of mappings would require some specific funding. Not a huge activity in the context of C3S: a long term commitment would be more important than large scale funding.

2.5 Match of Policy Actions to Long Term Goals

In the UK there is a Climate Change Committee which is set up to review the link between Government policy and the stated climate objectives. That is, it does not judge the objectives as such, but reviews the consistency between strategic aims and actual policy initiatives. This establishes a mechanism through which constructive feedback from the science and economic communities is fed into Government. The committee does not just meet and express their views .. it is a funded activity with resources to conduct appropriate levels of research to back up their reports.

There are 4 related strategic mitigation goals:

1. European and national emissions targets;
2. The Paris Accord targets for global emissions;
3. The Paris Accord targets for global temperature change;
4. The UNFCCC commitment to avoid dangerous climate change.

The scientific view on the links between these goals is evolving, sometimes quite rapidly, as events and improvements in scientific understanding give us a greater understanding of the processes involved. C3S could potentially play a significant role by facilitating an analysis of European policy and its fit to these mitigation goals

Summary

This is intended to provide an impartial view of service activities which, if given stability through C3S funding, would deliver significant benefits to the IPCC and UNFCCC. Some of the work could be done by CEDA, but the majority of it would necessarily be done by other centres where the relevant expertise is held. I have not consulted with all the people concerned ... it is hard to establish a common view on many things in the network of evolving networks that makes up the climate projections community. However, I believe that the summary above gives a fair overview of the relevant areas of activity.